

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.*	Colour	Analysis % ; Found/(Calcd.)		μ_{eff} ** B.M.
		M	N	
MnL ₂ (H ₂ O) ₄	Khaki	15.92 (15.74)	16.68 (16.05)	5.96
FeL ₂ (H ₂ O) ₄	Yellowish brown	16.20 (15.96)	16.46 (16.00)	5.20
CoL ₂ (H ₂ O) ₄	Reddish brown	16.63 (16.70)	15.92 (15.87)	4.62
NiL ₂ (H ₂ O) ₄	Green	16.68 (16.64)	16.00 (15.88)	3.24
CuL ₂ (H ₂ O) ₄	Blue	17.89 (17.77)	15.81 (15.66)	1.96

*L=C₄H₈N₂O₃⁻.
**At 308 K.

L=C₄H₈N₂O₃⁻. The copper complex starts decomposing at 130° and continues to lose weight upto 450° without any intermediate. The observed weight loss at 450° corresponds to the conversion of CuL₂(H₂O)₄ to CuO.

The iron(II) complex exhibits a doublet weak absorption band at 8 650 and 10 750 cm⁻¹ which may be assigned due to ⁵E_g←⁵T_{2g} transition. The doublet arises because the degeneracy of the E_g level is being lifted by Jahn – Teller and tetragonal distortions⁴. For the cobalt(II) complex the weak absorption band around 8 150, 16 200 cm⁻¹ and the strong band at 19 550 cm⁻¹ may be assigned to transitions ⁴T_{2g}←⁴T_{1g} (ν₁), ⁴A_{2g}←⁴T_{1g} (ν₂) and ⁴T_{1g} (P)←⁴T_{1g} (ν₃) respectively. The medium broad band around 8 650 cm⁻¹, the medium band around 13 980 cm⁻¹ and the strong sharp band at 26 050 cm⁻¹ of the nickel(II) complex may be assigned to the ³T_{2g}←³A_{2g} (ν₁), ³T_{1g}←³A_{2g} (ν₂) and ³T_{1g} (P)←³A_{2g} (ν₃) transitions, respectively. The medium broad band at 15 160 cm⁻¹ may be assigned to the spin-forbidden⁴ transitions ¹E_g←³A_{2g}. The value of Δ in the cobalt(II) complex is 8 050 cm⁻¹ and that in the nickel(II) complex is 8 650 cm⁻¹ indicating their octahedral stereochemistry. In comparison to oxygen coordinated uracil complexes⁵, the value of Δ in this case is higher by about 500 cm⁻¹. A strong broad band at 14 020 cm⁻¹ for the copper(II) complex refers its octahedral geometry.

The main area of interest in the ir spectra is in the region 1 800–1 300 cm⁻¹ where the ν_{C=O} and δ_{NH} bands of uracil is located. The position and intensity of the band due to the ν_{C(2)=O} and δ_{NH(1)} remain almost unaltered in the complexes with respect to that of the free uracil⁵. The position of the band due to ν_{C(4)=O+C=C} is shifted very little while that due to δ_{NH(3)} disappears completely in the complexes. The disappearance of the δ_{NH(3)} band in the complexes indicates that the coordination of the uracil in its anionic form to the metal ion takes place through N(3).

Acknowledgement

Authors are thankful to the University of Kalyani for providing a Research Fellowship to one of them (R.K.B.).

References

1. M. GOODGAME and K. W. JOHNS, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1978, 30, L835.
2. M. GUPTA and M. N. SRIVASTAVA, *Polyhedron*, 1985, 4, 475.
3. A. R. SARKAR and P. GHOSH, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1988, 78, L89.
4. A. B. P. LEVYER, "Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy", Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1967, p. 87.
5. H. SUSI and J. S. ARD, *Spectrochim. Acta, Part A*, 1971, 27, 1549.

Synthesis and Characterisation of some Transition Metal Complexes with Salicylaldiminobiacetyl Monohydrazone

E. M. SUBRAMANIAN, V. DURAI

and

S. BALASUBRAMANIAN*

Department of Inorganic Chemistry, A. O. College Campus, University of Madras, Madras-600 026

Manuscript received 24 August 1987, revised 25 April 1988, accepted 28 May 1988

CONJUGATED azomethine compound, viz. rhodopsin¹ is an important intermediate in the chemistry of vision. The *o*-hydroxyarylidine Schiff bases which are in the form of pyridoxal derivatives², are involved in transamination and racemisation reactions of α-amino acids. We report here the synthesis and characterisation of the complexes of bivalent Mn, Co, Ni, Cu and Zn with the Schiff base salicylaldiminobiacetyl monohydrazone (SALBAMH) (1) derived from biacetyl monohydrazone and 2-hydroxybenzaldehyde.

Experimental

Biacetyl (Fluka) was vacuum-distilled before use. 2-Hydroxy benzaldehyde was also distilled. Hydrazine hydrate (98–100%, B.D.H.) was dehydrated following the reported procedure³. Nitrogen was estimated by the micro-Kjeldahl method. Nickel and cobalt were determined by spectrophotometrically, copper by solvent extraction method and manganese and zinc complexometrically. Ir spectra (KBr) were obtained on a Shimadzu IR 408 spectrophotometer and electronic

spectra on a Hitachi 320 uv-vis spectrophotometer. Magnetic susceptibility measurements were made by the Gouy method⁴.

Synthesis of ligand (SALBAMH) : A solution of biacetyl (10 cm³, 0.115 mol) in dry benzene was cooled to 0° under nitrogen. Anhydrous hydrazine (4 cm³, 0.125 mol) was added in drops with stirring. The resulting white precipitate was filtered, washed and dried. To the biacetyl monohydrazone thus obtained (3 g, 0.015 mol), 2-hydroxy benzaldehyde (4 cm³, 0.038 mole) was added in dry benzene in N₂ atmosphere. The product that separated out after stirring the solution for 6 h at 0°, was filtered and recrystallised from benzene-petrol (50 : 50) mixture (60%), m p. 107–08°.

General method of preparation of complexes : The ligand SALBMAH (0.8 g, 0.004 mol) in ethanol was refluxed with sodium acetate trihydrate (0.01 mol) and the metal salt (0.002 mole) for ~3 h. The separated complex was filtered, washed with water and dried over calcium chloride. In the case of cobalt(II) and manganese(II) complexes the reaction was carried out in N₂ atmosphere; yield 30–40%.

Results and Discussion

The free ligand (I) in ethanol displayed two uv bands. The more intense band at 34 250 cm⁻¹ (17 725 M⁻¹ cm⁻¹) was attributed to $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition⁵ and the broad 28 900 cm⁻¹ band, which showed solvent sensitivity, was attributed to $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition. The absorption due to C=O group, which is also in conjugation, is likely to merge with $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition of C=N group. However, in the case of salicylaldehyde monohydrazone four bands were observed in its electronic spectra⁶ and the presence of only two bands in the present case may be due to the extensive conjugation in the ligand.

The ir spectra of the free ligand showed a strong band at 1 680 cm⁻¹ (C=O) and the peak at 1 620 cm⁻¹ is due to $\nu_{C=N}$ of the azomethine group. The broad band around 3 400 cm⁻¹ is due to ν_{OH} phenolic and the peak at 1 550 cm⁻¹ is assigned to the C=N–N=C moiety⁷. The nmr spectra of the ligand displayed a complex multiplet at δ 7.0–7.6 due to the aromatic ring protons and the methyl signal⁸ at δ 2.4–2.8. The singlet around δ 8.5 is assigned to phenolic proton.

The band due to C=N at 1 620 cm⁻¹ in the ir spectra of the complexes shifted by 45–80 cm⁻¹ on coordination. This negative shift indicates coordination through azomethine nitrogen and a greater extent of π -bonding between the metal atom and the ligand molecules¹⁰. The absorption due to hydroxyl group at 3 400 cm⁻¹ is not observed in the case of the metal complexes, indicating that deprotonation of the phenolic group has taken place during complexation.

The analytical data (Table 1) indicate 1 : 2 metal–ligand stoichiometry of the complexes. The complexes of manganese, cobalt, nickel and zinc

are soluble in common organic solvents while that of copper is sparingly soluble. The conductance measurements of the complexes in methanol indicate their non-electrolytic nature⁹.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.	Analysis % :		μ_{eff} B.M.
	Found/(Calcd.)		
	M	N	
Ni(C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₂) ₂	11.83 (12.63)	12.21 (12.05)	2.70
Co(C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₂) ₂	12.87 (12.68)	12.50 (12.04)	2.97
Mn(C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₂) ₂	11.47 (11.92)	11.90 (12.15)	2.52
Cu(C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₂) ₂	13.60 (13.53)	11.41 (11.92)	1.80
Zn(C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₂) ₂	14.19 (13.86)	11.46 (11.88)	Diamag.

The six-coordinate octahedral complexes of nickel(II) displayed three spin-allowed transitions in the visible region with low molar extinction coefficients. However, in the present system only one band at 21 750 cm⁻¹ (185.9 M⁻¹ cm⁻¹), which may be attributed to the ν_s transition, was observed. The other two bands which generally fall in the regions 7 000 and 11 000 cm⁻¹ were not observed. The cobalt(II) complex exhibited a band at 25 000 cm⁻¹ (980 M⁻¹ cm⁻¹). The higher ϵ value suggests that the $d-d$ band merges with a C–T absorption in this region. The manganese(II) complex showed one $d-d$ band in the visible region at 21 750 cm⁻¹ (302 M⁻¹ cm⁻¹). The higher ϵ value may be due to intensity stealing from C–T states. The copper(II) complex exhibited two bands in the visible region, at 22 550 and 27 200 cm⁻¹. The zinc(II) complex showed two peaks due to ligand transitions only.

The low values of room temperature magnetic moment (Table 1) for the nickel(II) complexes may be due to spin equilibrium¹¹. The above observations point to a distorted octahedral geometry for these complexes.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank Prof. P. Natarajan for his encouragement. One of the authors (E. M. S.) is grateful to U. G. C., New Delhi, for financial assistance.

References

1. M. AKHTAR, P. T. BLOSSER and P. B. DEWHURST, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1967, 631.
2. Y. MATSUSHIMA and A. E. MARTELL, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1967, **89**, 1822.
3. G. PANNETIER, M. BULTINGAINE and V. LIBORDE, *Bull. Soc. Chim. Fr.*, 1958, 1393.
4. P. W. SELWOOD, "Magnetochemistry", Interscience, New York, 1950.
5. A. B. P. LEVYER, "Inorganic Electronic Spectra", Elsevier, New York, 1984.

6. R. C. AGGARWAL, D. S. S. VARAPRASADA RAO and V. C. SEKHAR, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1981, 20, 622.
7. C. LORENZINI, C. PELIZZI, G. PELIZZI and G. PREDIERI, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton, Trans.*, 1983, 721.
8. S. C. JACKELS, K. FARMERY, E. K. BAREFIELD, N. J. ROSE and D. H. BUSCH, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1972, 11, 2893; A. M. TAIT and D. H. BUSCH, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1977, 16, 966.
9. W. J. GRAY, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1977, 7, 81.
10. A. M. FISHER and R. C. STOUFFER, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1966, 5, 1172.
11. C. J. O'CONNOR, *Prog. Inorg. Chem.*, 1982, 29, 204.

bases (1a-d) derived from 8-acetyl-7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin and 4-substituted anilines.

- 1a, X=H (Ahmcanil)
 1b, X=Me (4-Me-Ahmcanil)
 1c, X=Cl (4-Cl-Ahmcanil)
 1d, X=NO₂ (4-NO₂-Ahmcanil)

Formation Constants of Lanthanide(III) Complexes with 8-Acetyl-7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin Anils

GANESH P. POKHARIYAL

Department of Chemistry,
 M. M. College (Meerut University), Khakra-201 101
*Manuscript received 8 October 1987, revised 6 May 1988,
 accepted 28 May 1988*

Experimental

The Schiff bases (1a-d) were prepared by refluxing equimolar quantities of 8-acetyl-7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin (Ahmc) and aniline itself, or 4-methyl-, 4-chloro- and 4-nitro-aniline as the case may be in methanol for 30 min. The resulting orange-yellow crystals that separated on cooling were filtered, washed with aqueous 5% ethanol and finally recrystallised from methanol (Table 1).

IN continuation of earlier studies^{1,2} on the coordinating tendencies of coumarin and Schiff bases with the metal ions, I report here the formation constants of lanthanide(III) complexes with the Schiff

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND IR SPECTRAL (cm⁻¹) DATA OF COMPOUNDS

Compd. no.	M.p. °C	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)*			ν _{OH}	ν _{C=O}	ν _{C=N}
		O	H	N			
1a	191	73.8 (73.7)	4.9 (5.1)	4.5 (4.7)	3 280-3 380	1 720	1 610
1b	209	74.0 (74.2)	5.2 (5.5)	4.3 (4.5)	3 020-3 100	1 730	1 605
1c	202	65.6 (65.9)	4.0 (4.2)	4.0 (4.2)	3 010-3 090	1 720	1 600
1d	227	63.5 (63.9)	3.9 (4.1)	8.0 (8.2)	3 040-3 095	1 725	1 610

*Compd. 1c analysis : Found Cl, 10.6. Calcd. 10.8%.

TABLE 2—PROTON-LIGAND AND LANTHANIDE(III)-LIGAND CONSTANTS WITH Ahmcanil, Me-Ahmcanil, Cl-Ahmcanil and NO₂-Ahmcanil

Temp.=30°, Dioxane - Water=70% (v/v), I=0.1 M (NaClO₄)

	La	Ce	Pr	Nd	Sm	Gd	Dy
(a) Ahmcanil (pK _{OH} =8.50 and pK _{NH} =11.81)							
log β ₁	5.44	5.60	5.69	5.82	6.02	6.00	6.05
log β ₂	9.40	10.12	10.10	11.00	12.10	11.50	12.26
log β ₃	14.01	14.89	14.85	16.00	17.30	16.51	16.85
(b) Me-Ahmcanil (pK _{OH} =8.43 and pK _{NH} =11.72)							
log β ₁	5.80	6.20	6.41	6.41	6.80	6.61	6.85
log β ₂	10.70	11.45	11.81	11.54	12.71	12.01	12.70
log β ₃	15.05	15.50	15.16	15.34	17.60	16.49	17.00
(c) Cl-Ahmcanil (pK _{OH} =5.87)							
log β ₁	4.61	4.77	4.81	5.01	5.71	5.60	5.80
log β ₂	8.75	9.10	9.00	9.02	10.10	9.92	10.00
log β ₃	10.55	13.34	13.16	13.70	14.60	14.24	14.00
(d) NO ₂ -Ahmcanil (pK _{OH} =5.71)							
log β ₁	4.52	4.74	4.72	4.91	5.41	5.80	5.60
log β ₂	7.85	8.41	8.30	8.52	9.20	8.93	9.04
log β ₃	10.01	11.00	11.20	12.00	13.00	12.10	12.81